

Towards a General Theory of Rhythm

Microtime, Phrasing, and Functional Rhythm

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This document compiles four theoretical articles originally published at *general-theory-of-rhythm.org* in July 2015. They present the foundational concepts of the General Theory of Rhythm: a framework for describing, notating, and composing with microtime, phrasing, and functional rhythm. These concepts were first implemented computationally in the WohlTemperiertesPhrasierApparat (WTPA), a Max/MSP patch first published 24 July 2011 (Zenodo: 10.5281/zenodo.19385028).

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Basic Principles

What follows is not entirely up to date because I recently came to new representations of rhythm which I'd like to discuss in future articles. For now though, the good « old » model I've used for the past years is still accurate and will probably remain most suited when it comes to musical description and notation of rhythmic phenomena. It is also most adequate to stimulate and orientate instrumental practice.

However let me just mention here that the new representations of rhythm I'm working on are all about considering rhythms as a result of some kind of waveshaping applied to the the waving quality of Time. Together with physicist Andrea Giammanco from CERN we have started discussing analogies between the present theory and possibly existing mathematical models from the fundamental physics domain. These exciting discussions might be the premises of important theoretical developments with potential applications to electronic music software and hardware design.

So now, let's dive into the heart of the matter...

1- Phrasing

A rhythm pattern of n elements and with a total duration of t can be considered as an extremely phrased n -tuple over the duration of t .

Therefore there is a theoretical infinity of phrasings for any given n -tuplet. The straight n -tuplet is an exception rather than the norm, all other n -tuplets consisting of notes of unequal durations.

2– Morphing

Between this extremely phrased tuplet and the evenly distributed tuplet, there is an infinity of tuplets which can be attained while morphing gradually from the phrased tuplet to the evenly distributed tuplet. One such tuplet can be described through the amount of phrasing that it presents.

Hereunder a few examples:

i) Swing

ii) West african or Afro-cuban triplet

iii)

Gnawa triplet

iv) Gnawa or Brazilian 16th

v) Mad

professor Braff's phrased 5-tuplet

3- Groove

Tuplets happening over a duration equivalent to the pulse period can define microtime (or micropulse). A phrased microtime is termed *groove*. The amount of phrasing is then referred to as amount of *groove*.

When a groove is applied to the micropulsatory grid it reveals and reinforces the pulse. Indeed, the pulse's frequency becomes clearly perceptible thanks to the groove's recurring distorsion of the microtime cycle.

As I mentioned earlier in this article, I am currently working on new developments wherein I actually begin to consider that, rather than the micropulse, it is the time flow itself that is distorted. This notion is tied to the observation that the playing musician's time perception differs from the linear and evenly segmented time which is normally used to describe music. So instead of being linear, the time flow is happening in waves that present a recurring shape.

4-Tempered harmonisation

Through phrasing, distinct rhythmical harmonics can harmonise « more » in the sense that synchronisation points are multiplied. An added effect is a relative multifunctionality of each harmonic. In this regard, it is similar to the pitch temperament concept used in Western music. This opens a new field of observations and concepts that I call Functional Rhythm. I'll discuss this in more detail later as well.

5-Notation

To indicate phrasing, I add a system of small headless notes above the main staff. The durations of those small notes represent the relative durations of the phrased elements. The stems of those small notes are aligned with the notes of the main staff that they influence. The intensity of the phrasing is notated as a percentage. At 0%, the rhythm is played as notated in the main staff; at 100%, it is played as notated with the small headless notes.

One can also notate a small system of microtime notes with their phrasing to specify a groove feel that is applied over a whole portion of a piece. This groove can also variate as shown below:

Diversity of grooves: it's all about da weight !

23 juillet 2015 by Malcolm Braff — 1 Comment

Filtering Infinity

Soon after I began my practical study of the various grooves (phrasings) for different microtime divisions, their extraordinary diversity appeared: each of them has a different taste, a different feel, like the various accents which are applied to the different languages around the world. I wanted to explore this diversity of grooves and refine my ability to hear, identify, and play them on the piano.

In order to organize my practice I undertook to draw up a list of canonical patterns that I could morph from and consider as phrased tuplets. I first needed to reduce that list from a theoretical infinity of patterns to a set of patterns actually worth practising by taking out redundancies for example.

According to the theory, any rhythmical pattern can be considered a phrased tuplet. Also, any given tuplet can take up the function of a microtime if its total cycle coincides with the pulse cycle. But here's where psycho-acoustics also join the game :

Practically speaking, some phrased patterns can't be perceived as microtime. For example a pattern of three elements with duration ratios of 5:1:1 will never sound like a

triplet for the human brain. A 2:1 ratio is probably the upper limit that's never reached because at 2:1, the ear then tends to add the missing elements of a higher division. Here for example a 4-element pattern with durations of 2-1-1-2 will sound like a 6-element pattern with missing strokes 1-(1)-1-1-1-(1).

Beside duration ratios, another limitation is related to the range of perception of tempi (pulse frequencies). There is a lower limit of pulse frequency below which the human brain no longer feels a pulse and needs to subdivide in order to predict strokes with precision (apparently the limit can go as low as 0.2 Hz or 15 bpm, although for most people the limit is much higher). That's why long patterns are either not perceptible as microtime (because their total cycle exceeds this lower limit pulse cycle), or far too fast to be heard as micropulse (micropulse becomes pitch above 16Hz approximately), let alone to be phrased (nobody can swing eighth notes passed a certain tempo).

Last but not least one of the most interesting properties of some phrased microtimes is that they allow one to identify the pulse frequency out of the microtime structure itself, regardless of the pitches applied. This property has an important effect: the pulse feel is emphasized, creating a feeling which might as well be the very essence of what we call groove. In the case of patterns consisting of the repetition of smaller patterns, the induced pulse feel syncs with the cycle of the smaller pattern. For example a series of 6 swinging eighth notes is perceived as 3 times the swinging duplet (*ill., right*) rather than a 6-tuplet (*ill. left*).

Taking all these psycho-acoustic elements in consideration, I chose to limit my list of canonical patterns to those ranging from two to seven elements, made of non recurring combinations of long and short elements expressed with a ratio of 2:1, and thus notated using eighth and sixteenth notes beamed together (to the beat). Have a look at the list [here](#). The patterns are classified according to size and grouped in families of related patterns that are rotations of one another.

Of course there are much more patterns of interest to study. For instance patterns combining more than two different lengths, sometimes found in traditional music, have

special qualities. But practising the canonical patterns that I propose is enough to extend one's capacity to hear and perform very fine variations of phrasings and to quickly adapt to more complex ones if needed.

It's all about gravity

When it comes to classifying my canonical patterns I identify 4 parameters that I name *absolute size*, *tuplet size*, *potential energy* and *groove balance* :

- *Absolute and tuplet size:*

When considering the morphing between the pattern and its associated straight tuplet, one can say that it is a morphing between a high and a low division.

The *absolute size* represents the high division, and the *tuplet size* the low division.

tuplet size 5
absolute size 7

So the *tuplet size* of a pattern is simply the number of elements it contains, in other words what kind of tuplet it is considered to be a phrasing of, whereas the *absolute size* of a pattern is its duration expressed in 16th notes.

- *Potential energy:*

The *potential energy* describes how far a pattern and its associated straight tuplet are. In other terms it describes how much energy one needs to morph from the pattern to the straight tuplet and vice versa. The closer a pattern is to its straight tuplet, the easier it will be to morph back and forth between them. It is calculated by adding the distance between each element of the pattern and its corresponding element of the straight tuplet. Here below we find again the

previous 5(7)-tuplet illustrated in order to show the concept of potential energy.

- *Groove balance*

The *groove balance* describes whether a groove feel is laid back or pushing forward:

The pulse is often described as « ground ». This is probably because of dance where tapping the feet to the ground generally coincides with the pulse. In my view, « ground » could also depict the attraction exerted by the pulse's « ground-point »: the beat. Like a bouncing ball is attracted to the ground, the time flow's present is attracted to the beat.

Now depending on how we look at it, the beat can either be the point the bouncing ball lands on, or the point from which it takes off. Musicians will describe a beat or groove as « rushing », « pushing », « moving forward » or to the contrary as « sticky », « laid back », « pulling ». These different perspectives can actually be induced by the shape of the bouncing trajectory, i.e. the phrasing of the microtime.

So the shape of a phrasing pattern will affect the groove feel and make it more or less pushy or laid back. The *groove balance* describes that feel. To explain this better I'll use polygons inscribed in circles. They represent tuplet phrasing patterns, so triplets will be triangles, 4-tuplets will be squares, and so on. A regular polygon illustrates a straight tuplet whereas an irregular one illustrates a phrased tuplet.

Here, a circle represents the pulse's cycle and the vertices of the polygon represent the different elements of the rhythmic pattern. The downmost vertex represents the first element of the pattern. It shows the beat point, or « ground point » of the groove. There is a gravity arrow pointing towards the ground to show the attraction of the beat. All polygons stand on the ground point but will tip over to either side depending on their balance. Regular polygons are perfectly balanced because of the even distribution of their vertices on the circle so they stand in equilibrium over the ground point.

The illustration above features 3 different triplets: A is an equilateral triangle and represents a straight triplet. B and C are irregular triangles and represent phrased triplets. B tips over to the right and hence represents a « rushing » triplet. C on the contrary evokes a « laid back » feel.

I speak of negative and positive *groove balance* values. The theoretical values range between -1 (extremely laid back) and +1 (extremely pushy). They are

calculated by adding the signed potential energies of each pattern element, whereas the total *potential energy* of a pattern is calculated by adding the absolute values of the potential energies of each element.

- Herunder a form that calculates automatically the *tuplet size*, *absolute size*, *potential energy* and *groove balance* for a given pattern. Simply enter a pattern (for example 21121) in the appropriate field. Only works up to 7 digits.

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Inaccuracy of the common metric system

1 juillet 2015 by Malcolm Braff — [Leave a Comment](#)

Western music theory is based on the following rules and concepts to describe rhythm (except for a few exceptions which I won't discuss in this article) :

- Elements composing a musical piece are rhythmically defined by their time position and duration.
- Time is considered linear and a graduation system is used to measure and describe rhythm. The graduation divides time into units which in turn are subdivided into sub-units. The graduation is made in base 2: units are divided into two sub-units, divided in turn into two sub-sub-units and so on : halves (2), crochets (4), quavers (8), semi-quavers (16), etc.
- Units are commonly called *beats* and their frequency defines the *pulse* or *tempo* of the music, expressed in beats per minute. Sub-units represent the *micropulse* or *microtime*. Because a microtime is an integer division of the unit, its frequency is a harmonic of the pulse.
- Beats are grouped into longer periods (sub-harmonics) called *bars*. The bar-level is typically the only one that can afford other ratios than 2-exponents. The harmonic system that comprises the frequencies of the *bar*, the *pulse* and its subdivisions is called the *meter*.

- Micropulse frequencies that are not a 2-exponent of the pulse are exceptions and are called *tuplets*. They are expressed as a ratio towards another « regular », 2-exponent micropulse (for example, the triplet, expressed in relation to the quaver).

This Western metric system has now been used for centuries by music scholars to analyze, describe, study and teach music. It was also used as a reference to analyze music cultures and traditions other than its own.

However in my opinion this metric system fails to describe accurately the rhythm phenomena occurring when musicians play, especially when it comes to polyrhythmical music such as African or Afro-rooted traditional music. This I think, is due to two major problems/misconceptions :

- The Western metric system is a limited harmonic system, as there is always only one single level of subdivision : the pulse is divided into a single number of sub-divisions, which in turn are singly sub-divided and so on. Never does it allow the coexistence of different divisions. Although having the possibility of tuplets, the meter is « monophonic » or « biphonic » at most: the bar cycle plus one harmonic (the pulse division of the bar) with its octaves (2-exponent sub-divisions). This means that the meter does not, in essence, consider multiple harmonics of a fundamental frequency happening simultaneously. Instead, when facing music presenting multiple simultaneous divisions and because of its concept of musical time as a single grid of regular graduation, the metric system will attempt to reach for a common multiple of the frequencies in presence. For example, during my musicology studies I came across an ethnomusicology paper proposing that some African percussionist was playing with 1/100th of beat precision. This is nonsense to me, as it doesn't describe the actual neuro-cognitive process at work in the musician.
- Such a normalized metric system is unable to describe the phrasing that some musicians/cultures apply to their microtime. A microtime is termed *phrased* when some distorsion or *swing* is applied to the micropulsatory grid resulting into the feeling that the pulse is divided into uneven micropulses. Known examples of this are the *swinging eight-note* of course, but also the so-called *brazilian-sixteenth*, ore the recently popularized *Gnawa triplets and sixteenth*. I reckon that musical time is cyclic and that the playing musician does not perceive it as being linear.

Salsa is a major chord

5 juillet 2015 by Malcolm Braff — Leave a Comment

The Afro-cuban salsa rhythm comprises three major elements: the *beat* of course, the *clave* and *the cascara*. As shown below, the *cascara* can be seen as a phrased triplet while the *clave* can be considered a phrased 5-tuplet. Both tuplets harmonise towards the binary rhythm divisions which are octaves of the beat. So salsa rhythm is a harmonised system of three frequencies with a root plus its third and fifth harmonics. We can look at these rhythmic elements as three notes of a chord with the respective functions of the tonica (root), the fifth (3rd harmonic) and the major third (5th harmonic). Hence: *salsa is a major chord!*

The image displays three musical staves illustrating the rhythmic elements of salsa. The top staff, labeled *cascara*, shows four groups of three eighth notes, each bracketed with a '3' below it, indicating a triplet. The middle staff, labeled *clave*, shows two groups of five eighth notes, each bracketed with a '5' below it, indicating a 5-tuplet. The bottom staff, labeled *beat*, shows four quarter notes, each with a vertical line extending downwards from the stem, representing the basic pulse. The staves are connected by a vertical line on the left side.